

Supplementary figures

Figure S1: Mock community data. F1 score assessment of MetaHifiasm assemblies (left Zymo, right ATCC)

Figure S2: Mock community data. CheckM assessment of MetaFlye assemblies (left Zymo, right ATCC)

Figure S3: Mock community data. CheckM assessment of MetaHifiasm assemblies (left Zymo, right ATCC)

Figure S4: MetaBat2 results for *Apoderus coryli*

Figure S5: MetaBat2 results for *Mythemna impura*

Figure S6: Duplication level according to the BUSCO microsporidia_odb10 dataset of selected contigs and reassembly of the *Nosema* fraction in the *Mythimna impura* dataset.

Figure S7: MetaBat2 results for *Thunnus albacares*

Figure S8: MetaBat2 results for *Cladonia squamosa*

Figure S9: MetaBat2 results for *Chondrosia reniformis*